

CONTEMPORARY APPROACHES IN ASSESSMENT OF STUDENTS IN HIGH EDUCATION IN CASE OF DIGITAL EDUCATION

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Abstract: This paper describes the assessment and its role in education. The authors draw attention to assessment of learning in this highly technological society which challenges both learners and students. Personal experiences of teachers in assessment of students for and after learning is explained. It elaborates on the use of learning management systems in the state university. There is reference to research studies on this topic and gives a thorough understanding of the concepts. The article concludes with recommendations and further actions for the readers to take to improve teaching and assessment of students.

Key words: assessment, teachers, learning management system, Central Asian countries, student, teaching system, Classroom, subjects.

Introduction. Assessment has always been a challenging process in every educational setting. Pupils and students alike perceive it as a negative factor which demotivates and even frustrates some stakeholders, for example, parents and pupils themselves. However, people who are involved in assessing have experienced many issues including negative washback, unfair evaluation, infamous assessment techniques. Elturki (2020) highlights the need to explore assessment as it is an essential part of teaching and learning and it encompasses a variety of important parts including formative assessment, summative assessment, item analysis, principles of assessment, grading scheme and many others.

Assessment and Principles of assessment. In fact, many students in higher education have a phobia of assessment, test and other similar terms because they are to be marked. Although these terms seem to mean marking, grading, they are not only about that. Assessment is a general term which covers everything in the classroom and beyond it – learning, teaching, course materials, marking, results of students, and many others. Test developers should be cautious while designing test items because students will be affected with results. Thus, it is necessary for teachers to consider the principles of assessment. Our assessment must be reliable, practical, valid, authentic and open for washback.

By reliable, it is understood that students can rely on the tests test developers had created. Practicality – time and materials given to students are properly distributed and just for their level. Valid test measures students’ abilities based on what they had learnt in the classroom the whole semester. Authentic test prepares students to real-world tasks. Washback – teachers and students learn from their weaknesses and strengths after the test had passed (Akhmadjonov, 2023).

Table 1. Jones & Bartlett Learning (2021) recommend five innovative approaches to assess students.

Use large pools of questions and shuffle choices	Teachers can create as many questions as possible. Then the questions can be shuffled automatically digitally so that students will have different questions in the test.
Ask open ended and open book questions	Close ended questions like multiple choice and true/false questions are good to assess but their use can be limited online. It is recommend using open ended questions as they are more practical and convenient digitally.
Integrate learning technologies	A variety of learning technologies are used to assess students formatively and summatively at Cornell University include: Canvas - a learning platform where different assessment tools are used: quizzes, discussions, peer assessment, assignments In-Video Quizzes - students watch videos to test their understanding of assignments Classroom Polling - teacher asks questions and they can get answer instantly. This can take place in the classroom or outside.
Use multimedia projects	Students at Ursinus College used multimedia to remix their findings using digital tools. The teacher called Johanna Mellis encouraged her students to use this method. The results of her study showed that it is fun for students to make their projects and a new way for teachers to assess. In the study these tools were used: StoryMaps, Fakebook, Microsoft Sway, TimelineJS Other additional options include: podcasts, video, digital

	drawing, and writing
Use collaborative testing	Students will not be tested individually rather they will collaborate to explore responses to questions and they come up with innovative ideas.

Our personal experiences.

At our university, we used Moodle education platform. It had a variety of functions in the test section. We could shuffle words by just clicking the button which would shuffle a ton of questions in a second. This helped to avoid plagiarism. Students had similar question items but mixed so that students can focus only on their own.

In Moodle learning system, we used to assess students through giving open-ended questions. We would insert a question and students should write a paragraph, essay or an article. It is really practical for teachers to assess. Secondly, teachers do not have to print out paper which is always shortage. Third, students and teachers can save time and instead they can do something valuable.

LMS (learning management system)

At the university of World Economy and Diplomacy, LMS (learning management system) is used. It is really practical and cost-effective (see Figure 1). Teachers can oversee the flow of student works and student performance is effectively evaluated. It is relative a new way of assessing students since before we could not evaluate students' abilities digitally. Also, students and professors can track their work performance easily.

Figure 1. A screenshot of LMS system: my personal university account

This system is called LMS and it is really handy to check student performance. it can be accessed through the website: www.lms.uwed.uz. Only, you need to have access to the internet connection and must be registered. This can be done with the permission of the administration. On the left side of the platform (see Figure 1), there is a menu of some functions.

HOME: When I click on the home button, it shows dashboard with all news and upcoming deadlines. It helps teachers to keep track of coming assignments.

AUDITORIUM FOUND: in this window, teachers can have a look at rooms which are occupied and which are not. Sometimes, it is possible to make changes if there is need for better room with necessary equipment.

SCHEDULE: in this window teachers can see the schedule of their subjects. The days and time of lessons are located there. The room number, name of the subject, level, and the group name can be found there.

SUBJECTS: There is information about subjects, class id, the number of credits, and code of the subject. Coloring is used to determine the level of student academic year. In this section, teachers can assess their students. For this, first, assignments will be added with assessment criteria. Students can see the task assigned on their own account and they upload their files to be evaluated. Using the scoring criteria will assess them in the LMS platform. For, they should enter STATEMENT section.

Figure 2. The general content of the subject and the topics of lessons

In Figure 2, it can be seen that teachers can follow the lessons in their own profile. They can insert new materials and assign tasks which will show deadlines on

the window. This is practical for teachers since it enables them to evaluate the creativity of students and assess their performance.

Figure 3. A screenshot of the window which shows how students are marked

Ведомость - Английский язык IV 2022 (Upper-Intermediate)			
Срок проставления оценок студентам: 6 дней после окончания срока сдачи			
ZENU202		Language focus: Listening	Language focus: Writing
№	Макс. балл	5	7
1	Abdusalimov Behruzbek	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Alimov Shohriyoz	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Ataxanova Jasmira	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Beginqulova Malika	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Jafarov Javohirmirzo	5	<input type="checkbox"/>
6	Nurullayeva Samirabonu	5	<input type="checkbox"/>

Marking students in LMS is straightforward (see Figure 3) and content-based because first teachers upload their tasks to be done in the given time period and then students should follow it if they want their performance marked appropriately and reliably. The principles of assessment are fully employed in LMS because it is practical, reliable, and valid. Washback can also be given digitally or face to face. Arslonbekova (2023) points out that learning takes place when students are aware of what they have to do, when they have to and how they have to do. Thus, transferring teachers' work into digital environment will help students see what teachers are expecting from them.

When setting the goal of developing educational processes, it is essential to consider the specific characteristics and needs of each region and its people. Batoriva (2024) points out that language teachers need to spend sufficient time on preparing for lessons in ESP classes. In this regards, understanding their social and economic conditions, geography, climate, infrastructure, customs and traditions, values, political situation, and other relevant aspects is crucial for making decisions and setting strategic plans based on scientific findings. The successful implementation of an advanced educational system throughout the Central Asian states is likely to contribute significantly to overcoming these challenges.

For example, in 2000s, German education system faced significant challenges. This can be attributed to the following factors:

- Lack of comparative study and evaluation of the German education system with other countries' education systems.

- German education professionals considering the German education system as one of the strongest in the world, which might have led to complacency and hindered recognition of shortcomings.

- Insufficient recognition of the educational achievements of migrants, resulting in a lack of diversity and inclusion within the system.

The German government focused its attention on developing the following directions to quickly address the situation:

A. Upgrading the current national education system standards, particularly in mathematics, natural sciences, and foreign languages.

B. Enhancing the quality of education for migrants.

C. Incorporating modern scientific theories into educational practices.

D. Reducing the dependence of the education system on the state.

E. Empowering teachers to have more autonomy and independence.

F. Increasing competition in the education sector through the "Education Alliance" initiative.

In their successful development of education within a short period, Singapore pays particular attention to the following factors:

Ø the role of private education to increase on the basis of regular competition;

Ø adequate state investment in education.

Ø National educational institutions are not governed by “Super Governors” but by the Association of professors or the academic council;

Ø excellence of texts in educational literature and textbooks;

Ø high family income.

If we observe the current trends in education, we can see that artificial intelligence and digitalization are increasingly being integrated into teaching practices. However, certain regions still face traditional challenges associated with education. For instance, in the Central Asian states, the education system has yet to find solutions to the following issues:

The fact that the syllabus was inherited from the USSR;

Many study hours and subjects from the norm;

Limited opportunities for creative and integrated learning due to time constraints;

Insufficient emphasis on the conceptual and scientific foundations of the curriculum;

Inadequate salaries for teachers and their lack of sufficient experience;

Disparity between rural and urban areas in the education system;

The presence of issues such as the lack of alignment with the credit module system.

Conclusion. In sum up, ways to assess students are many, but we teachers should be selective and careful in choosing the appropriate tools for our student learning outcomes. The educational setting where we work can help teachers to transfer their working place into digital world. Digital learning conforms with the trends of this globalized society. In every sphere, particularly, education, digitization has become commonplace so LMS allows teachers to teach, share, and assess students properly.

From the above analysis, we can conclude that education, in any form, plays a crucial role in improving the individual's life and contributing to the overall socioeconomic development of society. In the Central Asian states, transitioning from "super leadership" in education to a management system emphasizes that managers should not only address administrative issues but also engage in scientific activities through advisory roles. While this approach has been utilized in foreign experiences, in Central Asian countries, education personnel have not been fully separated into distinct roles for teaching and scientific activities.

References.

1. Akhmadjonov, K. A. (2023). Students' Performance In Russian And Uzbek Language Instruction Classes. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(16), 435–437. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/5003>
2. Arslonbekova, R. A. (2023). Who are better learners: monolinguals, bilinguals or multilinguals?. *SCHOLAR*, 1(35), 181–184. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10442328>
3. Batirova, M. (2024). Strategies for esp teachers. *Innovative development in educational activities*, 3(9), 134–138. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11187850>
4. Jones & Bartlett Learning. (2021, September 16). *Innovative Assessment Strategies in Higher Education*. Retrieved from <https://www.jblearning.com/blog/jbl/2021/09/16/innovative-assessment-strategies-in-higher-education>
5. Elturki, E. (2020). A systematic process for assessing assessment. *English Teaching Forum*, 58(4), 12-21.

